

ISSN (o): 3030-3362

No 3(25)

27.03.2025

IF 2024
11.7

RTADQIQ VA TATBIQ

Research and implementation

scientific-methodical journal

SCIENCE S

Exact, Natural, Political, Social, Economic, Technical, Medical, Pedagogical

INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CERTIFICATE
№ 078777

 rai-journal.uz

 [@ferteach_uz](https://twitter.com/ferteach_uz)

Editor in Chief:

F.M.Mukhtarov
PhD, associate prof

Executive editor

S.I.Zokirov
PhD, associate prof

Languages:

Uzbek, Russian, English and
Karakalpak

Registered in the Agency of
Information and Mass
Communications under the
Administration of the
President of the Republic of
Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023
under number 078777.

[IF-2024: 11.7](#)

[@feritech_uz](#)

+99893-343-13-14

<https://rai-journal.uz>

Editorial Board:

B.R.Ismailov – Dr. Tech. Sc., Prof., M.Avezov South Kaz. Univ., Shymkent, Kazakhstan
I.Bjorn – Ph.D., Imeritus, Technical University of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark
A.Rasulov – Dr. Phys.-Math. Sc., Prof., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
L.K.Mamadaliyeva – Dr. Tech. Sc. (DSc), Prof., FerPI, Fergana, Uzbekistan
M.E.Yunusaliyev – Dr. Tech. Sc. (DSc), Prof., FerPI, Fergana, Uzbekistan
X.B.Ismailov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., M.Avezov South Kaz. Univ., Shymkent, Kazakhstan
J.T.Moldaliyev – Can. Bio. Sc., Assoc. Prof., OshSU, Osh, Kyrgyzstan
O.S.Nazarmatov – DSc in Econ., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
G.K.Obidova – DSc in Ped., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
T.M.Abdullayev – Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
N.I.Ibrokhimov – Ph.D. in Phys.-Math., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
A.R.Nurmatov – Ph.D. in History, NamSU, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
T.Yu.Bakirov – PhD in Ped. Sc., FarSU, Fergana, Uzbekistan
D.F.Tukhtasinov – Ph.D. in Ped. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
S.B.Atajonova – Ph.D in Ped. Sc., AndMI, Andijan Uzbekistan
Sh.A.Umarov – Ph.D. in Phys.-Math. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
I.A.Rustamov – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
B.Kh.Tolipov – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
O.Kh.Otakulov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
O.S.Raimjonova – Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
R.A.Nurdinova – Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
M.I.Ismoilov – Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
I.T.Tojiboyev – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana State University, Uzbekistan
Sh.J.Kholmatov – PhD., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
Z.N.Khatamova – PhD. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
Q.Kh. Akhunov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
M.Kh. Okhunov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
A.Q. Khomidov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
Sh.Sh. Akramov – PhD, TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.A. Salimov – PhD in Econ., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
Z.G'. Ubaydullayev – Can. Econ., TUIT Qarchi Branch, Qarchi, Uzbekistan
S.S. Ibragimov – Ph.D in Tech. Sc., AndMI, Andijan Uzbekistan
Sh.J. Kholmatov – Ph.D. in Phil., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
G.D. Kuchkarova – Ph.D. in Phil., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
I.R.Teshabayeva – Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.L.Meliqzuyev – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
O.U.Kholmatova – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
N.N.Radjabov – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Oriental University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
Sh.A.Yuldashov – Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., Fergana State University, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.A.Yuldashev – Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., Fergana State University, Fergana, Uzbekistan
M.Israilov – Can. Tech. Sc., Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan Academy of Forces
N.S.Abdullaeva – PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDU, Namangan, Uzbekistan
A.G.Turgunboyeva – PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDPI, Namangan, Uzbekistan
M.A.Abdullaeva – Prof., NamDU, Namangan, Uzbekistan
I.O.Ergashev – PhD in Econ., Fiscal Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
N.T.Mamatxanova – PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDPI, Namangan, Uzbekistan
U.Yu.Akhundzhanov – PhD in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
O.M.Ergashev – PhD in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
N.R.Khallieva – PhD in Econ., Bukhara MTI, Bukhara, Uzbekistan
F.K.Achilova – Can. Econ. Sc., TUIT Qarchi Branch, Qarchi, Uzbekistan
A.K.Samyayev – PhD in Geog., Sam. Reg. Ped. Skills Center, Samarkand, Uzbekistan
J.S.Abdullayev – Can. Phys.-Math. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
N.D.Botirova – PhD in Ped, TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan

Bosh muharrir:

F.M.Mukhtarov
PhD, dotsent

Ijrochi muharrir:

S.I.Zokirov
PhD, dotsent

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, Rus, Inzliz va
Qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi Axborot va
ommaviy
kommunikatsiyalar agentligi
tomonidan 2023-yil 3-
mayda 078777 raqami bilan
ro'yxatga olingan..

IF-2024: 11.7

@ferteach_uz

+99893-343-13-14

<https://rai-journal.uz>

Tahrir hay'ati:

B.R.Ismailov – t.f.d., prof. M.Avezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston
I.Byorno - Ph.D., Imeritus, Daniya Texnika Universiteti, Kopengagen, Daniya
A.Rasulov – f.-m.f.d., prof.TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
L.K.Mamadaliyeva – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
M.E.Yunusaliyev – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
X.B.Ismailov- t.f.n., dot., M.Avezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston
J.T.Moldaliyev - bio. f. n., dotsent. OshDU, Osh, Qirg'iziston
O.S.Nazarmatov - iqt.f.d. DSc, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
G.K.Obidova - ped.f.d. DSc, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
T.M.Abdullayev – t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
N.I.Ibrokhimov – f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
A.R.Nurmatov – tarix f.b. Ph.D., NamDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
T.Yu.Bakirov - ped. f.b. PhD, FarDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
D.F.To'xtasinov - ped.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
S.B.Atajonova - ped.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston
Sh.A.Umarov - f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
I.A.Rustamov - fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
B.X.Tolipov - f.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
O.X.Otaqulov – t.f.n., dotsent. TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
O.S.Raimjonova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
R.A.Nuridinova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
M.I.Ismoilov – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
I.T.Tojiboyev – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona davlat universiteti, O'zbekiston
Sh.J.Kholmatov - i.i.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
Z.N.Khatamova - t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
Q.X. Axunov - t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
M.X. Oxunov - t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
A.Q.Xomidov - t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
Sh.Sh.Akramov – q.x.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.A.Salimov - iqt.f.b. PhD, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
Z.G'.Ubaydullayev - iqt.f.n., TATU Qarchi filiali, Qarchi, O'zbekiston
S.S.Ibragimov - t.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston
Sh.J.Xolmatov- fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
G.D.Kuchkarova- fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
I.R.Teshabayeva - t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.L.Meliquziyev- fil.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
O.U.Xolmatova- fil.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
N.N.Radjabov- fil.f.b. Ph.D., dotsent, Oriental University, Toshkent, O'zbekiston
Sh.A.Yuldashov - t.f.b. Ph.D., Farg'ona davlat universiteti, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.A.Yuldashev - t.f.b. Ph.D., Farg'ona davlat universiteti, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
M.Israilov - t.f.n., O'zbekiston Respublikasi Qurolli Kuchlar Akademiyasi
N.S.Abdullayeva - p.f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston
A.G.Turg'unboeva - p.f.b. PhD, NamDPI, Namangan, O'zbekiston
M.A.Abdullayeva - professor, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston
I.O.Ergashev – iqt.f.b. PhD, Fiskal instituti, Toshkent, O'zbekiston
N.T.Mamatxanova - p.f.b. PhD, NamDPI, Namangan, O'zbekiston
U.Yu.Axundjanov - t.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
O.M.Ergashev - t.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
N.R.Xallieva - iqt.f.b. PhD, Buxoro MTI, Buxoro, O'zbekiston
F.K.Achilova - iqt.f.n., TATU Qarchi filiali, Qarchi, O'zbekiston
A.K.Samyayev - g.f.b. PhD, Sam. vil. ped. mah. mar, Samarqand, O'zbekiston
J.S.Abdullayev - f.-m.f.n., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
N.D.Botirova – ped.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

Torch infeksiyasi kelib chiqish sabablari, profilaktikasi va davolash choralari

Mo'minov Azamat*, Mutallibova Oyshaxon Jamoliddin qizi, Kumushoy Saliyeva

Kokand university Andijon filiali

Ilmiy rahbar

Copyright: © 2025 by the author.

Licensee: This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Annotatsiya. Maqolada ushbu infeksiyalarning kelib chiqish sabablari, ular orqali yuqish yo'llari va xavf omillari tahlil qilinadi. TORCH –infeksiyalarning asosiy etiologik omillari sifatida viruslar, bakteriyalar va parazitlar ko'rsatiladi. Infeksiyaning yuqish odatda transplatsentari yo'l orqali sodir bo'ladi, ammo ba'zi hollarda jinsiy aloqa, qon quyish yoki kontaktdan keyin yuqishi ham kuzatiladi va bularning barchasi haqida ushbu maqolada batafsil so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: torch, sifilis, cmv, urogenital herpes, uchuq

Причины, профилактика и лечение TORCH-инфекции

Моминов Азамат*, Муталибова Ойшахон Джамолиддин кызы, Кумушой Салиева

Андижанский филиал Kokand University

**Научный руководитель*

Аннотация. В статье проанализированы причины этих инфекций, пути их передачи и факторы риска. Показаны основные этиологические факторы TORCH-инфекций: вирусы, бактерии и паразиты. Заражение обычно происходит трансплацентарным путем, но в ряде случаев передача происходит. Также наблюдается после полового акта, переливания крови или контакта, и все это подробно рассмотрено в этой статье.

Ключевые слова: факел, сифилис, цмв, уrogenитальный герпес, чипс.

Causes, prevention and treatment of TORCH infection

Mominov Azamat*, Mutallibova Oyshakhon Jamoliddin qizi, Kumushoy Saliyeva

Kokand University Andijan Branch

**Scientific Supervisor*

Abstract. The article analyzes the causes of these infections, the ways of their transmission and risk factors. Viruses, bacteria and parasites are shown as the main etiological factors of TORCH infections. The infection usually occurs through the transplacental route, but in some cases, transmission is also observed after sexual intercourse, blood transfusion or contact, and all of these are discussed in detail in this article.

Key words: torch, syphilis, cmv, urogenital herpes, chips

Kirish.

Torch-infektsiyalar — har qanday yosh va jinsdagi odamlarga ta'sir qilishi mumkin bo'lgan, ammo faqat homiladorlik uchun tayyorgarlik ko'rayotgan va homilador ayollarga, homila va yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarga nisbatan qo'llaniladigan atama. Homiladorlik paytida TORCH guruhining har qanday infektsiyasi bilan birlamchi infeksiyalanish xavfli sanaladi, shuning uchun bu infeksiyalarga antitana mavjudligini aniqlashga qaratilgan qon tahlilini topshirish maqsadga muvofiq hisoblanadi

Asosiy qisim.

Torch – Infektsiyasi homiladorlik davrida o'ziga xos xavf tug'diruvchi infeksiyon kasalliklar guruhiga kiradi. Ushbu infeksiyalar homiladorlik davrida homila rivojlanishiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi, konjenital patologiyalar va hatto homilaning yo'qolishiga olib kelishi mumkin. TORCH abbreviaturasi quyidagi infeksiyalarni anglatadi:

T-Toksoplazmoz

Hujayra ichida yashovchi obligat protozoy parazit. Parziting yakuniy xo‘jayini mushuklar va mushuksimonlar oilasining boshqa vakillari sanaladi. Bundan tashqari, bu parazit atrof –muhitda keng tarqalgan va boshqa ko‘plab sutemizuvchilarda, shu jumladan odamlarda ham aniqlanadi. Dunyo aholisining uchdan bir qismidan ko‘prog‘i bu parazit tashuvchisidir.

O – Boshqa (other): sifilis, gepatit B va C, HIV, parvovirus B19 va boshqa

R- Qizamiqcha (rubella)

Sog‘lom oamdan bemordan , ko‘pincha havo tomchilari orqali yuqadigan yuqumli virusli kasallik. Qizilcha deyarli zararsiz bo‘lgan “bolalar“ infeksiyasi sanalib ,qoida tariqasida , bu hech qanday jiddiy oqibatga olib kelmaydi.

Biroq agar homilador ona qizilcha yiqtirib olsa bu zararsiz infeksiya homilaning nobud bo‘lishiga olib kelishi mumkin . Homiladorlikning dastlabki bosqichida qizilcha virusi ko‘pincha asab to‘qimalari , ko‘z to‘qimalari va yuragiga ta’sir qiladi.

C-sitomegalovirus (CMV)

Dunyodagi eng keng tarqalgan infeksiyalardan biri, herpes oilasining eng yashirin viruslaridan sanaladi. Sitomegalovirus bilan birlamchi infeksiyalanish homilador ayollar uchun xavflidir , chunki infeksiya rivojlanayotgan embrionga ham o‘tishi mumkin.

H-Gerpes

Vanihoyat, TORCH infeksiyalaridan oxirgisi-bu herpes. Umuman olganda, herpeskasallil ham emas, balki virusli infeksiyon kasallikdan iborat butun guruh hisoblanadi. Oddiy herpes viruslarning ikki guruhi ma'lum –I va II tip:

I Tipdagi herpes, ayniqsa, ko'pchilikka ma'lum bo'lgan lablardagi" uchuq" ko'rinishida namoyon bo'ladi.

II Tipdagi herpes ko'p hollarda jinsiy a'zolariga ta'sir qiladi (urogenital herpes deb ataladi).

Herpes havo tomchilari orqali va jinsiy yo'l bilan, shuningdek , "vertical ravishda" , ya'ni homilador onadan yo'ldosh orqali homilaga o'tishi mumkin.

Ammo, agar ma'lum bir infeksiyaga qarshi antitanalar soni juda ko'p bo'lsa yoki vaqt o'tishi bilan ko'payib borsa, bu infeksiyon jarayonning faolligini ko'rsatadi. Bundan tashqari, klinik jihatdan kasallik o'zini namoyon qilmasligi yoki xira, aniq bo'lmagan shaklida namoyon bo'lishi ham mumkin. Kasallikning tashqi ko'rinishining jiddiyligi uning homilaga xavfli ta'siri bilan bog'liq emas. Kasallikning aniq namoyon bo'lishida homila sog'lom bo'lib qolishi va aksincha, klinik ko'rinish kuzatilmagan taqdirda — homila jiddiy shikastlanishi yoki shikastlanmasligi mumkin. Qonda IgM antitanalari infeksiyalanishdan 2-4 hafta o'tgach paydo bo'ladi va 3-9 oydan keyin yo'qoladi. 3-4 haftaga kelib IgG antitanalari paydo bo'ladi, ularning konsentratsiyasi asta-sekin ko'tarilib, infeksiyadan 2-5 oy o'tgach, cho'qqiga chiqadi. IgG antitanalari qonda uzoq vaqt saqlanib turadi, ba'zan esa butun hayot davomida. Agar homiladorlikni rejalashtirgan ayolda, shuningdek, 12 haftalikkacha qadar bo'lgan homilador ayollarda IgM antitanalariga salbiy va IgG antitanalariga ijobiy natija aniqlansa, bu infeksiyaga qarshi immunitet mavjudligidan dalolat berishi mumkin. Agar aksincha, IgM antitanalariga tahlil ijobiy natija, IgG antitanalariga esa ijobiy / manfiy natija aniqlanadigan bo'lsa, buna hozirda o'tkir jarayon borayotganini taxmin qilish mumkin. Bunday holda, IgG sinfidagi antitanalarning avidlik testi o'tkaziladi, bu kasallikning davomiyligini aniqlashga yordam beradi, bu homiladorlikning 12 haftasiga qadar ehtimoliy infeksiyada ayniqsa muhimdir.

Oldini olish

Homiladorlikni rejalashtirishdan oldin, shuningdek homiladorlikning erta muddatlarida TORCH kompleksi qo‘zg‘atuvchi agentlariga nisbatan antitanalar mavjudligini aniqlash uchun qon tahlili topshirish juda muhimdir. Agar homiladorlikdan oldin ayolning qonida ushbu infeksiyalarga IgG sinfidagi antitanalar aniqlansa, ayol bemalol homilador bo‘lishi mumkin — bu infeksiya uning homilasiga tahdid solmaydi. Agar homiladorlikdan oldin TORCH kompleks infeksiyalariga ushbu antitanalar aniqlanmasa, ayol o‘zini va bolasini himoya qilishi kerak.

Davolash choralari:

Toksoplazmoz: pirimetamin va sulfadiazine preparatlari, foliy kislatasi qo‘shilishi bilan davolanadi.

Qizamiqcha: homiladorlik paytida maxsus davolash yo‘q. Emlashdan oldin rejalashtirish muhim.

Sitomegalovirus : antiviral preparatlar (gansiklovir) tavsiya qilinadi.

Gerpes: asiklovir yoki valasiklovir qo‘llaniladi/

Sifilis : penetsilin asosidagi antibiotiklar bilan davolanadi.

Xulosa.

Torch infeksiyasiylari homiladorlik davrida va chaqaloq salomatligi uchun katta xavf tug‘dirish mumkin. Bularning oldini olish uchun vaqtida tekshiruvlardan o‘tish, gigiyena va emlash qoidalariga rioya qilish muhimdir. Davolash esa infeksiya turi va homiladorlik davriga bog‘liq holda individual tarzda belgilanadi. Shunday ekan har bir inson nafqat o‘zining balki atrifdagilarni ham sog‘ligiga befarq bo‘lmaslik lozim. Hozirgi kunda tibbiyotga qaratilayotgan e‘tib tufayli har qanday kasalliklarni ham davolash ishlari kashf etilmoqda .

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Ayupova F.M. Ginekologiya
2. Ya.N.Allayorov. Akusherlik va ginekologiya –
3. Nargiza Magzumova. Ginekologik kasalliklar- 4.med360.uz
5. <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/nima-uchun-homiladorlar-torch-infeksiyasiga-tahlil-topshirishi-shart>
6. <https://med24.uz/uz/uslugi/ginekologiya/torch-kompleks>
7. Klinik protokollar (ginekologiya) - Ushbu nashr S.M.Kirov nomidagi harbiy – tibbiyot akademiyasi akusherlik va ginekologiya kafedrasini jamosi tomonidan tayyorlangan.

Scientific-methodical journal “Research and implementation”

Address:

150100, Fergana region, Fergana, Solim street, 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@rai-journal.uz

Our website:

<https://rai-journal.uz/>

The Scientific-methodical journal “Research and implementation” was founded by LLC Fer-Teach and supports by the Fergana branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi. This journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023 (No 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

"Research and implementation" is a specialized journal in the field of technology and covers all major areas of research and development in various fields of technical sciences: physics, mathematics, information technology. The journal also publishes scientific articles on linguistics, teaching methods and the history of the development of technical sciences.

Languages: Uzbek, Russian, English, Karakalpak

ВНИМАНИЕ!

При использовании материалов журнала необходимо указывать источник
Авторы статей несут ответственность за содержание статей и за сам факт их публикации.

Редакция не всегда разделяет мнения авторов и не несет ответственности за недостоверность публикуемых данных.

Редакция журнала не несет никакой ответственности перед авторами и/или третьими лицами и организациями за возможный ущерб, вызванный публикацией статьи.

ATTENTION!

When using journal materials, you must indicate the source.

The authors of the articles are responsible for the content of the articles and for the very fact of their publication.

The editors do not always share the opinions of the authors and are not responsible for the unreliability of the published data.

The editorial board of the journal does not bear any responsibility to the authors and / or third parties and organizations for possible damage caused by the publication of the article

DIQQAT!

Jurnal materiallaridan foydalanganda manbani ko'rsatish kerak.

Maqola mualliflari maqolalar mazmuni va ularning nashr etilishi fakti uchun javobgardirlar.

Har doim ham mualliflarning fikrlari tahririyat nuqtai nazarini ifodalamaydi va nashr etilgan ma'lumotlarning haqiqiyliги uchun javobgar emas.

Jurnal tahririyati mualliflar va/yoki uchinchi shaxslar va tashkilotlarga maqolaning e'lon qilinishi natijasida yetkazilishi mumkin bo'lgan zarar uchun javobgar emas.